

1 **Supplementary Figure Caption**

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4 Fig. S1. The picture outside the cave at SBCB station.

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7 Fig. S2. The picture inside the cave at SBCB station.

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12 Fig. S3. The picture of the seismometer and recorders at SBCB station.

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15 Fig. S4. The picture of the seismometer at SBCB station.

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